

ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ МНОГОЗНАЧНОСТИ ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация.

В статье идёт речь о многозначности слов как своеобразных единиц лексики, которые служат для выразительности и красочности художественную речь (ассоциативно связанных между собой и образующих сложное семантическое единство).

Ключевые слова.

Речь, полисемия, ассоциация, слово, многозначность, метафора, синекдоха, метонимия, омонимия, стилистическая омонимия ...

ELEMENTS OF POLYSEMINATION OF THE LANGUAGE

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Annotation.

The article deals with the polysemy of words as peculiar units of vocabulary that serve for expressiveness and colorfulness of artistic speech (associatively related to each other and forming a complex semantic unity).

Key words.

Speech, polysemy, association, word, polysemy, metaphor, synecdoche, metonymy, homonymy, stylistic homonymy...

Often, when they talk about polysemy, they mean, first of all, the polysemy of words as units of vocabulary. Lexical polysemy is the ability of one word to serve to designate different objects and phenomena of reality (associatively related to each other and forming a complex semantic unity).

For example: sleeve - sleeve ("part of the shirt" - "branch of the river"). The following relationships can be established between the meanings of a word:

- Metaphor

For example: horse - horse ("animal" - "chess piece")

A metaphor in the literature is called a hidden comparison.

"Clean air pouring through the window" (I. Bunin).

"In the brilliance of lights, behind mirrored glasses, Expensive flowers bloom luxuriantly ..." (I. Bunin).

"The endless road Runs off into the distance with a ribbon." (S. Yesenin).

"Puffing your ears with the ringing of the stars." (S. Yesenin).

"And we will come across the plains To the truth of the sewing cross
With the light of a dove book To drink your lips. (S. Yesenin).

"And plunge into the unknown, And hide your steps in it ..." (B. Pasternak).

"I grew up. And woven Complime A veil wrapped around me. (B. Pasternak).

"It is in front of her, flooding the barriers, The rapid is drowning in the vapour,

With a lamp of a hanging waterfall To a steeper with a hiss nailed. (B. Pasternak).

- Metonymy

For example: dish - dish ("type of dishes" - "portion of food")

Let us give examples of metonymy found in the works of the classics of Russian literature.

"All flags will visit us" - the word "flags", A. S. Pushkin, here means "countries".

"Where a peppy sickle walked and an ear fell ..." - an expression with metonymy from the poem "There is in the original autumn ..." by F. I. Tyutchev.

"The pen breathes his revenge" - "pen" was used by A. Tolstoy instead of the word "poetry".

"I ate three plates ..." - an example of metonymy from the fable of I. A. Krylov "Demyanova's ear".

"Weak packaging" (M. Zoshchenko).

"I pointed a lorgnette at her and noticed that my impudent lorgnette annoyed her in earnest" (M. Yu. Lermontov).

"Hey beard! And how to get from here to Plyushkin bypassing the master's house? (N.V. Gogol).

"I will send you a sweet dream, I will put you to sleep with a quiet fairy tale, I will tell you a sleepy fairy tale, as I watch over children" (A. Blok).

- Synecdoche

Examples of the use of synecdoche in literature

All flags will visit us. (A.S. Pushkin)

In this context, flags (part) means countries (whole) that will establish ties with Russia.

We read from N.V. Gogol in the novel "Dead Souls":

- Hey beard! And how to get from here to Plyushkin?

The writer called the man a beard according to one characteristic feature in his appearance. And a visible image of this man with a thick beard appeared before the reader. This is the artistic trope - the synecdoche.

In the fairy tale of Charles Perrault, the little girl is called Little Red Riding Hood because of one headdress that stands out in her outfit - a red cap that her mother gave her for her birthday.

The old red-haired head with sideburns again appeared from behind the door, looked and entered the office along with its rather ugly body. (I.S. Turgenev)

Only the hewn back of his head, sighing noisily, whispered. (A.M. Gorky)

The artistic trope of synecdoche occurs when the singular number of a noun is used as a plural in the text of a work.

And it was heard until dawn how the Frenchman rejoiced. (M.Yu. Lermontov)

Swede, Russian stabs, cuts, cuts. (A.S. Pushkin)

A distinction should be made between polysemy and homonymy. In particular, the word "key" in the meanings of "spring" and "musical sign" are two homonyms.

Stylistically, polysemy can be used to give expressiveness to speech. Masters of fiction in their works reveal the semantic shades of polysemantic words, often invisible in everyday use.

Based on the second chapter, we can be convinced that not only classics but also new authors are not averse to using polysemic words in their works. In particular, Blok liked to use metonymy, and this gave his poems a deeper meaning and charm.

It should be said that a large amount of literature is devoted to the problem of polysemy, which indicates the great interest of lexicologists in the phenomenon of polysemy. Many books were studied in the process of writing this article. The results only prove the relevance of the problem of polysemy in the Russian language. There is no doubt that the phenomenon of polysemy includes many aspects and requires much deeper research.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Abaev V.I. Speech at the discussion on homonymy // Leksikogr. Sat. Moscow: Progress, 1960, no. 4.
2. Apresyan Yu.D. Formal language model and representation of lexicographic knowledge // VYa, 1990, No. 6.
3. Arutyunova N. D. Metaphor in the language of feelings // Arutyunova N. D. Language and the human world. - M., 1999.
4. Arutyunova N.D. Language and the human world. Moscow: Progress, 1998.
5. Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. Ed. 4th, stereotypical. Moscow: KomKniga, 2007.
6. Budagov R.A. Introduction to the science of language. Moscow: Dobrosvet, 2000.
7. Bulakhovsky, L.A. Introduction to linguistics. Part 2. M.: Uchpedgiz, 1953.